

PEDAGOGICAL POSSIBILITIES OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' ECOLOGICAL CULTURE IN TOURIST ACTIVITIES

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The development of ecotourism in Uzbekistan not only helps to solve the problems of our spirituality, science, culture, enlightenment, nature protection, attracting ecotourists, preserving biodiversity, but also contributes significantly to economic issues, improving the socio-economic conditions of our local people, providing new jobs, and growing our country's economy. Our country is among the countries in the world rich in ecological tourism resources and is a country in Central Asia that geographically connects the countries of the world. Therefore, we have great potential for the strengthening of domestic and international tourist flows and ecotourism flows. In the second half of the 20th century, the development of technical innovations, the product of human consciousness and thinking, and the transition to an industrial society, which determined the criteria for development, simultaneously posed a huge number of complex problems for humanity, which, due to the scale and significance of their sphere of influence, were called global problems. As a result, various environmental problems of a local, regional, and universal nature arose, which are increasingly threatening the continuation of human civilization. At the same time, the majority of the world's population emphasizes that environmental problems such as ecosystem destruction and environmental pollution pose a great threat to humanity. Today, it is a requirement of the times to organize an approach to the environmental issue that threatens the life of humanity as an integral and main factor in the education of young people from the perspective of the future. It is necessary to emphasize the inextricable connection between the scientific and theoretical aspects of instilling ecological education in students and the system of practical and historical knowledge. This approach serves as the basis for the formation of an ecological culture in pedagogy, allowing for the successful mastering of interactions with nature in accordance with the concept of ecological education, and is considered a component of the "Ecological Education" factor. The term "ecological education" is a relatively new concept in pedagogy, but the problem of the interaction of man and the environment, nature has been considered from different perspectives throughout the history of the pedagogical approach. The implementation of ecological education is of particular importance in pedagogical historical teaching approaches, and the process of ecological education and upbringing is considered from the perspective of the formation of the human personality, its integrity, the unity of man and nature, society and the universe. According to the point of view of YA.A. Komensky, who put forward the view that a person has a natural, independent and self-motivating force, based on the regularity of education, the student forms a theory of the

principle of self-motivation in understanding the world and acquiring the necessary knowledge.

The views and theories about the emergence of a child's attitude to nature and its relationship from an early age also played a special role in the work of J.J. Rousseau, who emphasized that, from his point of view, the "natural development" of a child is based on the three combinations of upbringing, namely, the interaction and constant connection of nature, people and society. Also, according to J.J. Rousseau, in the process of education, the child must obey the laws of nature. In the process of natural education, the child's inclinations and needs should be taken into account, and the idea of aligning them with life knowledge that is necessary for social obligations is put forward. Treat your student physically and spiritually, depending on his age, take him out into nature every day, let him run there and fall several times, this process will give him the opportunity to get up faster, that is, to determine and restore his life position himself. Considering educational problems only within the framework of an educational institution is a one-sided view and does not provide sufficient basis for making the right decisions in this regard. Therefore, in the formation of a child's personality, the environment - nature, family, social institutions, state and non-state organizations, state policy and economy - also have their place, and, performing certain functions and tasks, they play a significant role in ensuring a systematic balance in coordinating the mutual relations between the school and the environment, which are directly related to the problems of environmental education at the level of the sphere of influence. In this regard:

- school education implements a system of environmental education in its activities;
- creates modern programs to increase the effectiveness of propaganda and agitation to instill in students an interest in the environment and love for living nature and the fact that they are a part of it;
- teaches students at school not only to study the environment, but also to be its active consumers, thereby teaching them that it is the only source of survival in the future;
- in school education, the balance of society and healthy thinking are explained through theoretical sources and practical factors that are a product of nature and the ecosystem;
- instilling progressive ideas, modern views and theories on the environment and ecotism in young people, increasing their social activity and getting rid of conservative views.

These views can have an impact on the active development of the problems of "ecological pedagogy" and serve as a theoretical and practical factor in the formation of new views on environmental education and upbringing in young people.

The analysis of the "ecological pedagogy" education shows that it allows schoolchildren to identify a number of key approaches that are important for the development of a modern environmental education system, and requires the inclusion in the subject program, in particular, the essence of the environment and its pedagogical significance, substantiation of its place in the education system, the study of various types of the environment, the development of methodological issues for organizing pedagogical work with the environment, issues such as "indicators" and "units of measurement". Based on this, supporters of the concept of "environmental pedagogy" emphasized the need to study the natural factors, laws, forms and methods of organization that affect the formation of a person, the entire process of social formation of a person as a continuous integral.

The development of the theory of "ecological pedagogy" made it possible to consider new perspectives in organizing environmental and environmental education. The ideas of the

educational environment, scientifically analyzed above, developed primarily as problems of social education, and a unique experience of creating an "open" pedagogical system in pedagogy, primarily in close contact with the natural environment, was formed. About these views and theories, researcher V.A. Sukhomlinsky put forward a number of scientific theories, and he says that educating a person through contact with nature encompasses the entire pedagogical system he created.

Regarding the ecological issue, on April 12, 2019, on the occasion of the International Day of Environmental Knowledge, the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in cooperation with the Eco-Movement deputy group and the Committee on Ecology and Environmental Protection, discussed in detail the issue of "Development of environmental education and upbringing in our country", emphasizing the need for high environmental knowledge to eliminate environmental problems that are becoming increasingly acute in the world. It focuses on issues of scientific and practical considerations, recognizing that Environmental Education Day is widely celebrated in many countries of the world every year, and that the promotion of environmental education among the world's population for the life and sustainability of humanity was comprehensively outlined at the UN Conference on Environmental Issues held in Rio de Janeiro in 1992. The intended goal is to promote the idea of enriching the ecological knowledge of the population of our planet, to develop an ecological culture among the population, to raise public awareness of the ecological safety of society, and to promote the upbringing of each citizen in the spirit of respect for nature.

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